

Effect of Rotational Shifts Schedule on the Well-being of Public & Private Nurses of Sindh: Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Research objective: To assess the effect of rational shift schedules on the well-being of public and private nurses in different hospitals in Sindh.

Study Design: It was a descriptive Cross-Sectional Study.

Place and duration of Study: The research was carried out at five different Public and Private hospitals; public hospital included (R.B.U.T) Civil Hospital Shikarpur, Ganga Bai Women (HGBW) Hospital Shikarpur, Civil Hospital Jacobabad and Private Hospital included Dr. Zeenat Isani Institute of Medical Sciences (ZIMS) Shikarpur, Jacobabad Institute of Medical Sciences (JIMS) Jacobabad. Moreover, this study started from 25th January 2025- to 25th February 2025. **Material and Methods:** The targeted population included all the hospital nurses who are working in different wards of the hospitals including Intensive Care Unit (ICU), Emergency Room (ER), Female Surgical Ward (FSW), Male Surgical Ward (MSW), Female Medical Ward (FMW), Male Medical Ward (MMW), Pediatrics Ward (PW), Neonate Intensive Care Unit (NICU), Nutritional Ward (NW), and Gynecology (GW). A convenient sampling method was used for data collection. The total sample size was 108, which was obtained through open EPI. **Results:** The table (01) shows that the male frequency is n=29 (26.8%), and the female frequency is n=31 (28.7%). This table also revealed that the female frequency is slightly higher than the male frequency. Moreover (table 02) shows that the male frequency is 32 (29.6%), whereas the female frequency is n=16 (14.81%). This table also revealed that the male frequency is higher than the female frequency. (Table: 03) shows that the age limit from 20-30 years, where the frequency was (n= 47) and Percentage (43.5%); moreover, the age limit from 30-40 years, where the frequency was (n=53) and Percentage (49%), this table also revealed that the frequency of age limit from (40-50) n=8 where Percentage is (7.4%). **Conclusion:** This study revealed that any institution that wants to serve patients around the clock must have shift workers. Shift work is necessary for nurses to provide continuous, high-quality care, yet it has specific negative implications on patient safety and nurses' health. Adverse impacts can be social, psychological, spiritual, or bodily. Shift workers have complained of headaches, exhaustion or fatigue, and Stomach problems. Shift employment has been positively linked to mental health issues like stress and anxiety.

Keywords: Effect, Rotational Shifts, Well-being, Nurses.

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INTRODUCTION

Nursing blends art, science, and compassion to provide comprehensive care. It prioritizes health, well-being, and optimal functioning while preventing illness, promoting healing, and alleviating suffering [1]. The detective investigation and the therapy of individuals' feedback and championing in looking after people, their peers, and social groups affiliated with compassionate treatment is termed Nursing [1]. A registered nurse has various roles and responsibilities, such as assisting physicians, analyzing medical history, educating patients about their disease and medicines, performing patient assessments, etc. [2]. In the multidisciplinary healthcare team, nurses play a vital role as they are involved in treatment protocols and fulfilling different roles in patient care [3]. Nurses provide care to patients worldwide by working in hospitals day and night [4]. Moreover, shift work, especially rotating shifts, is standard in the nursing field; nurse's work between 10 to 12 hours during shift work, and the shift sometimes begins in the morning, evening, or night shifts [5]. In a rotating shift schedule, the shifts can change frequently, sometimes daily, from one day being a night shift and the next day being a morning shift; the shifts are unpredictable and frequently change, avoiding a repetitive pattern [5]. In rotating shift work, high proportions of hospital nurses engage globally, disrupting their circadian rhythms, which can throw off their natural body clocks and lead to possible health issues due to a mix of complex factors [6]. During rotating shifts, circadian rhythms disturb nurses. Some factors include diverse external stimuli, frequent light exposure, some dietary behavior, physical activity, social stimuli (i.e., perceived stress), and sleep patterns [6]. Nurses in shift-based roles encounter distinct challenges that surpass ordinary work-related stress; research reveals that shift work can lead to severe consequences, including sleep disturbances, persistent fatigue, and a heightened risk of developing chronic health issues like cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and gastrointestinal problems [7]. Rotating-shift nurses are more prone to suffer from unusual sleep patterns and sleep disorders than nurses who work fixed day shifts. Rotating shifts disrupt the body's natural rhythm, making nurses sleepier, more fatigued, and less alert [8]. Social isolation is also one of the causes of nurses working rotating shifts, as reported by some studies [9]. Research indicates that psychological impacts are also significant among shift-working nurses, with elevated rates of stress, Burnout, and mental health issues, including anxiety and depression [8].

Problem of the Study

The research documented that female staff who work rotating night shifts have more chances of getting breast cancer due to decreased levels of melatonin and other hormonal imbalances [10]. ; Research circadian rhythm disruptions cause the majority of reproductive health problems among rotating shift nurses has revealed that it negatively impacts the job satisfaction of nurses and reinforces them to leave the job [11-13]. Working rotating Shifts raises the risk of overweight,

duodenal ulcers, and cancer in nurses [14]. So, this study aims to identify the effect of rational shift schedules on nurses' well-being.

Research objectives: To assess the effect of rational shift schedules on the well-being of public and private nurses in different hospitals in Sindh.

Significance of Study: Researching rotating shift work is more significant because it identifies different actual and potential health problems that arise in nurses, and disturbance of circadian rhythm leads to many physical and psychological issues [15, 16]. Moreover, the primary significance of this study is to explore how rotating shifts may affect nurses' social lives, and due to this n, nurses' interpersonal relationships are disturbed. Furthermore, this study may be convenient in creating how to manage rotating shifts, like advance schedule planning, adjustable schedule, delegating rotating shifts, encouraging support teamwork, fostering healthy lifestyle habits, granting access to wellness programs, and exchanging shifts.

Search Strategies Different search engines were utilized during the filtration, including PUB-Med, Google Scholars, CINHAL, and EBSCO. The articles were filtered from the past 10 years, 2015-2025. A total of 50 articles were filtered during searching, and only 15 articles were added to the Literature review.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Setting: This study was a quantitative cross-sectional study, which was started on 25-01-2025 and completed on 25-02-2025. The research was carried out at five different Public and Private Hospitals; the Public hospital included (R.B.U.T) Civil Hospital Shikarpur, Hira-nand Ganga Bai Women (HGBW) Hospital Shikarpur, Civil Hospital Jacobabad, and Private Hospital included Dr. Zeenat Isani Institute of Medical Sciences (ZIMS) Shikarpur, Jacobabad Institute of Medical Sciences (JIMS) Jacobabad.

Study Population: The targeted population included all hospital nurses who work in different wards of the hospitals, including the Intensive Care Unit (ICU), Emergency Room (ER), Female Surgical Ward (FSW), Male Surgical Ward (MSW), Female Medical Ward (FMW), Male Medical Ward (MMW), Pediatrics Ward (PW), Neonate Intensive Care Unit (NICU), Nutritional Ward (NW), and Gynecology Ward (GW).

Sample Size: The sample size calculated through Cochran's formula was $n=108$. After adding the total population of the five hospitals, which was 148, the confidence interval was 95%, and the margin of error was 0.05.

Sampling Technique: A convenient sampling method was used for data collection.

Research Tool

A questionnaire consisted of six sections.

Section A: Demographic of the Public and Private Hospital nurses, including Name, Age, Gender, Designation, Institute, Contact number, Department, and Qualification.

Section B: Questions regarding rotating shifts consist of 7 items.

Section C: Physical health consists of items:

Section D: Mental health consists of 7 items.

Section E: Social health consists of 6 items. **Section F:** Spiritual health consists of 4 items.

Inclusion Criteria: All hospital ward nurses were part of the data collection.

Exclusion Criteria: Those who were on leave were part of the exclusion criteria, and the excluded nurses were n=04:

Data Collection Tool: The questionnaire was adopted to assess the impact of the rotation shift on nurses' health working in public and private sector hospitals in Peshawar [17]. The pilot study was done through the questionnaire on 10% of the total population sample, and the internal consistency of the questionnaire is 0.8 to 0.9.

Data Collection Procedure: The data was collected with the permission of the principals and then with the permission of the MS (Medical Superintendent) of the Public and Private hospitals. A consent form and verbal instruction were given to nurses, and each nurse took 15 minutes to complete the form. Moreover, the questionnaire was collected again for data analysis.

Data Analysis: The data were analyzed using the latest version of SPSS V.25. The frequency and percentage of demographic data were calculated, and the mean of tables 07, 08, 09, 10, and 11 were also calculated.

RESULT

Demographic Analysis (Section: A):

Table 01: Classification based on Gender in Private Hospitals

CATEGORIES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Male	29	26.8
Female	31	28.7
Total	60	55.5

The (table: 01) shows that the male frequency is $n=29$ (26.8%), and the female frequency is $n=31$ (28.7%). This table also revealed that the female frequency is slightly higher than the male frequency.

Table 02: Classification based on Gender in Public Hospitals

CATEGORIES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Male	32	29.6
Female	16	14.81

Total	48	44.4
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The (table: 02) shows that the male frequency is $n=32$ (29.6%), and the female frequency is $n=16$ (14.81%). This table also revealed that the male frequency is higher than the female frequency.

Table 03: Classification based on Age Limit

AGE LIMIT	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
20-30 years	47	43.5
30-40 years	53	49.0
40-50 years	8	7.4
Total	108	99.9

(Table 03) shows that the age limit from 20 to 30 was ($n=47$), and the Percentage was (43.5%). Moreover, the age limit from 30 to 40 was ($n=53$), and the percentage was (49%). This table also revealed that the frequency of the age limit from 40 to 50 was ($n=8$), and the Percentage was (7.4%).

Table 04: Classification based on Professional Qualification

QUALIFICATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
DIPLOMA	60	55.5
BSN	48	44.4
Total	108	99.9

(Table 04) shows that the Professional Qualification from Diploma holders was ($n= 60$), and the percentage was (55.5%). Moreover, the Professional qualification from BSN holders was ($n= 48$), and the Percentage was (44.4%).

Table 05: Classification based on Work Experience

WORK EXPERIENCE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
05-10 years	22	20.3
10-15 years	33	30.6
15-20 years	50	46.3
20-30 years	3	2.7
Total	108	99.9

The (table: 05) shows that the work experience from 05-10 years, where frequency was ($n= 22$) and Percentage (20.3%), and the work experience from 10-15 years, where frequency was ($n= 33$) and Percentage (30.6%). Moreover, the work experience from 15-20 years, where the frequency was ($n=50$) and Percentage (46.3%), this table also revealed that the frequency of work experience from (20-30) $n=3$ where Percentage is (2.7%).

Table 06: Classification based on Area of Work

WORK AREA	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
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Intensive Care Unit (ICU)	22	20.4
Emergency ward (EW)	9	8.3
Female Surgical Ward (FSW)	4	3.7
Male Surgical Ward (MSW)	5	4.6
Female Medical Ward (FMW)	5	4.6
Male Medical Ward (MMW)	3	2.8
Gyne Ward (GW)	27	25
Peads Ward (PW)	13	12.0
Peads (NICU)	15	13.9
Nutritional Ward (NW)	5	4.6
Total	108	99.9

The (table: 06) shows that $n= 22$ (20.4%) were working in ICU, $n=9$ (8.3%) were working in ER, $n= 04$ (3.7%) were assigned in FSW, $n=05$ (4.6%) were working in MSW, $n=5$ (4.6%) were working in FMW, $n=3$ (2.8%) were assigned in MMW, $n=27$ (25%) were working in GW, $n=13$ (12%) were working in PW, $n=15$ (13.9%) were assigned in P(NICU), $n=5$ (4.6%) were working in NW.

Table 07: (Section: B) Distribution of nurses' regarding Rotating shifts Questions

S.NO	QUESTIONS	FREQUENCY		PERCENTAGE		MEAN
		YES	NO	YES	NO	
01	Do you work in a rotation?	92	16	85.1%	14.8%	0.8519
02	Are you satisfied with rotating shift work?	40	68	37.0%	62.9%	0.3704
03	Do you having a knowledge that working in a rotation may affect health?	92	16	85.1%	14.8%	0.8519
04	Which one of the health problem you are facing due to rotational duty?					
	Mental Health Problem	n=36		33.3%		0.3333
	Physical Health Problem	n=44		40.7%		0.4074
	Social Health Problem	n=21		19.4%		0.1944
	Spiritual Health Problem	n=7		6.5%		0.0648

Figure 01: Health Problem due to Rotational Shift

Figure 01 demonstrates that most nurses are suffering from physical health due to rotational shifts.

Table 08: (Section: C) Distribution of the nurses' according to Physical effect of rotating shift

S.N O	QUESTIONS	FREQUENCY		PERCENTAGE		MEAN
		YES	NO	YES	NO	
01	Do you have experienced with headache?	79	29	73.1%	26.8%	0.7324
02	Have you ever been constipated in shift work?	39	69	36.1%	63.8%	0.3611
03	Do you have stomach problems?	50	58	46.2%	53.7%	0.4630
04	Do you feel fatigue in shift hours?	82	26	75.9%	24%	0.7593
05	Do you visit to doctor for any of the physical health problems?	45	63	41.6%	58.3%	0.4167
06	Which kind of calories you mostly used in diet?					
	Carbohydrate	n=12		11.1%		0.1111
	Protein	n=19		17.6%		0.1759
	Fats	n=12		11.1%		0.1111
	All of them	n=65		60.1%		0.6019
07	If you having headache which type of headache you have?					
	Migraine	n=19		17.6%		0.1759
	Sinus	n=15		13.8%		0.1389
	Cluster	n=8		7.4%		0.0741
	Tension	n=66		61.1%		0.6111

(Table: 08) shows that $n= 12$ (11.1%) nurses used carbohydrates in their diet, with a mean score of 0.1111. $N=19$ (17.6%) nurses used protein in diet, with a mean score of 0.1759. Furthermore, $n=12$ (11.1%) nurses used fats in their diet, with a mean score of 0.1111, and $n=65$ (60.1%) nurses used all of them (carbohydrate, protein, fats) in their diet, with a mean score of 0.6111. Moreover, this table shows that $n=19$ (17.6%) nurses experienced migraine headaches in rotating shifts, with a mean score of 0.1759. Furthermore, $n=15$ (13.8%) nurses experienced sinus headaches on the rotating shift, with a mean score of 0.1389, and $n=8$ (7.4%) nurses experienced cluster headaches on the rotating shift, with a mean score of

0.0741. Finally, the frequency of tension headache $n=66(61.1\%)$ with a mean score of (0.6111) is higher than other types of headache in rotating shift.

Table 09: (Section: D) Distribution of the nurses' according to Psychological effect of rotating shift :

S.N O	QUESTIONS	PERCENTAGE				MEAN
		FREQUENCY		YES	NO	
		YES	NO			
01	Are you sleeping normally?	74	34	68.5%	31.4%	0.6852
02	Do you get enough sleep after night duty?	45	63	41.6%	58.3%	0.4167
03	Did rotating shift work effect your meal time?	82	26	75.9%	24%	0.7593
04	Proper intake of food could reduce the chance of getting mental problems?	66	42	61.1%	38.8%	0.6111
05	Do you visit to doctor for any of the mental health problems?	13	95	12%	87.9%	0.1204
06	For how many hours do you sleep in circadian rhythm?					
	<5 hours	n=22		20.4%		0.2037
	6 to 8 hours	n=65		60.1%		0.6019
	>8 hours	n=21		19.4%		0.1944
07	Which shift mostly disturbs your sleep pattern?					
	Morning shift	n=8		7.4%		0.0741
	Evening shift	n=7		6.4%		0.0648
	Night shift	n=93		86.1%		0.8611

Table (09) shows that $n=8(7.4\%)$ nurses experienced sleep disturbance in the morning shift, with a mean score of 0.0741, and $n=7(6.4\%)$ nurses experienced sleep disturbance in the evening shift, with a mean score of 0.0648. Furthermore, the frequency of sleep disturbance is higher, $n=93(86.1\%)$, with a mean score of 0.8611 in the night shift than in the morning and evening shift.

Table 10: (Section: E) Distribution of the nurses' according to Social effect of rotating shift

S.N O	QUESTIONS	FREQUENCY		PERCENTAGE		MEAN
		YES	NO	YES	NO	
01	Are you interested in social activities?	75	33	69.4%	30.5%	0.6944
02	Do you fulfill your social activities?	49	59	45.3%	54.6%	0.4537
03	Do you have proper to get engage with your family?	73	35	67.5%	32.4%	0.6759
04	Do you participate in the social activities of your community?	53	55	49%	50.9%	0.4917
05	Do you have friends in your community?	82	26	75.9%	24%	0.7593
07	In which of the following game you mostly participate with your friends?					
	Cricket	n=74		68.5%		0.6852
	Football	n=9		8.3%		0.0833
	Volley ball	n=7		6.5%		0.0648
	Hockey	n=7		6.5%		0.0648
	Gym	n=11		10.1%		0.1019

Table (10) shows that $n=74(68.5\%)$ nurses participated in cricket with their friends, with a mean score of 0.6852. Moreover, $n=9(8.3\%)$ nurses participated in football, with a mean score of 0.0833, and $n=7(6.5\%)$ nurses participated in volleyball, with a mean score of 0.0648. Similarly, $n=7(6.5\%)$ nurses participated in hockey, with a mean score of 0.0648, and only $n=11(10.1\%)$ nurses participated in the gym.

Table 11: (Section: F) Distribution of the nurses' according to Spiritual effect of rotating shift

S.N O	QUESTIONS	FREQUENCY		PERCENTAGE		MEAN
		YES	NO	YES	NO	
01	Do you offer your prayer properly?	60	48	55.5%	44.4%	0.5556
02	Are you involved in religious activities?	72	36	66.6%	33.3%	0.6667
03	Are you willing to get support/discussion for any problem with religious person?	52	56	48.1%	51.8%	0.4815
04	Do you believe that rotating shift hour	75	33	69.4%	30.5%	0.6944

have effect on your spiritual health?					
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(Table: 11) shows that $n=60(55.5\%)$ nurses offered prayer properly, with a mean score of 0.5556, and $n=48(44.4\%)$ nurses could not offer prayer due to rotating shifts. Furthermore, $n=72(66.6\%)$ nurses were involved in religious activities, with a mean score of 0.6667, and $n=36(33.3\%)$ nurses could not be involved in religious activities due to rotating. Similarly, $n=52(48.1\%)$ nurses were willing to get support for any problem with a religious person, with a mean score of 0.4815, and $n=56(51.8\%)$ nurses were not willing. Lastly, $n=75(69.4\%)$ nurses believed that rotating shift hours affect their spiritual health, with a mean score of 0.6944, and $n=33(30.5\%)$ nurses do not believe that rotating shifts affect their spiritual health.

DISCUSSION

In this article, a study [18] was done in Karachi, where most nurses were working in the private sector, rotating shifts compared to the public sector. The finding of our study indicated that the male ratio of nurses working in rotating shifts is greater than the female nurses working in rotating shifts, similar to the study done by [17] in Peshawar, where male nurses were in the majority as compared to female nurses working in rotating shifts. A study [19] done in Iran aligning with this study showed that most nurses were satisfied with their shift work. An aligning study [20] done in Korea showed that most nurses feel fatigued during rotating shifts. A study [21] similar to this one done in Spanish cities shows that most participants do not have stomach problems during their shift work. In contrast to the study [22] done in Palestine, the age limit of nurses was mainly between 20 and 30 years, as this study contains the majority of nurses aged between 30 and 40 years. In alignment with the study [23] done in Peshawar, most nurses working in rotating shifts were diploma Holders. Another study [24] analogous to this study done in Saudi Arabia shows that most nurses get 6 to 8 hours of sleep during their rotating shifts. The study [25] parallel to this study shows that most nurses cannot fulfill their social roles due to rotating shift work. Kindred to this study [17] was done in Peshawar, where most of the nurses working in rotating shifts had experience more than 5 years.

CONCLUSION

Any institution that wants to serve patients around the clock must have shift workers. Shift work is necessary for nurses to provide continuous, high-quality care, yet it has negative implications on patient safety and nurses' health. Adverse impacts can be social, psychological, spiritual, or bodily. Shift workers have complained of headaches, exhaustion or fatigue, and Stomach problems. Shift employment has been positively linked to mental health issues like stress and anxiety. The primary cause of disturbed sleep patterns is that working night and rotational shifts disrupt sleep patterns. It indicates that they have reported experiencing insomnia, sleeplessness, or sleep disorders. Eating habits during shift work changes: Eating late at night alters the regular schedule. 63% of Nurses do not get enough sleep after night duty. Moreover, 79% of nurses experience headaches during rotational shift work.

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Indicate the level of contribution of each author. All authors should include biographies with photo at the end of regular papers. Personal profile which contains details about their email id, education, publications, research work, membership, and achievements with photo and will be maximum 100-150 words.

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